

Exploring Medication Prescribing Patterns and Biochemical Parameters in Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome

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INTRODUCTION

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS), is a complex endocrine-gynecological disorder characterized by the overproduction of androgens, typically male sex hormones found in small quantities in women.[1] A pilot cross-sectional study undertaken in Tamil Nadu revealed an 18% prevalence of polycystic ovary syndrome among young adolescent females. [2] This study also noted a higher prevalence of PCOS among urban women compared to their rural counterparts. Similarly, an urban community-based study conducted in Mumbai reported PCOS prevalence rates of 22.5% according to the Rotterdam criteria and 10.7% according to the Androgen Excess Society criteria.[3] Another investigation among medical students at a private medical college in southern India, utilizing the modified Cronin questionnaire comprising 10 items, highlighted PCOS as a prevalent disorder among participants, with a noted high incidence of mood disorders.[4] In contrast, a study in Lucknow focusing on college-going women with menstrual irregularities and hirsutism in the age range of 18-25 years reported a lower prevalence of 3.7% using the NIH criteria.[5] Additionally, a study in Andhra Pradesh examining young women from a residential college found that 9.13% of them satisfied the Rotterdam criteria for PCOS.[6] Vidya Bharathi et al. demonstrated a 6% prevalence of PCOS diagnosed by the Rotterdam criteria in community-dwelling women from both rural and urban areas of Chennai. [7] International studies have reported PCOS prevalence ranging from 4-10% among women of reproductive age. [8] The variation in prevalence rates across these studies in India may be attributed to differences in the criteria employed for PCOS diagnosis. Thus, based on the available data, the prevalence of PCOS in India appears to range from 3.7% to 22.5%. Infertility is a significant concern, affecting between 70% and 80% of women with PCOS. This infertility is often linked to enlarged and dysfunctional ovaries, elevated androgen levels, and insulin resistance. Genetics play a crucial role in PCOS, with familial inheritance patterns observed across generations. However, there can be variations in the presentation and severity of the condition among individuals and families.[9] Moreover, PCOS is frequently associated with long-term health complications, both physical and mental, further impacting the well-being of affected individuals. [10] Obesity and insulin resistance are common risk factors associated with PCOS, potentially exacerbating its symptoms and complications. Therapeutic approaches for PCOS can vary significantly, necessitating personalized strategies tailored to address the primary symptoms and therapeutic goals of each individual. However, there is a notable lack of comprehensive data in published literature regarding the global prescription patterns for PCOS, including in regions like India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This observational study aimed to analyze demographics, prescribing patterns, and biochemical parameters in female patients aged 18-35 years diagnosed with Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome. Participants included female patients aged 15-25 years with a confirmed diagnosis of PCOS. Inclusion criteria were: Diagnosis of PCOS based on established clinical and/or biochemical criteria. Age between 15 and 25 years at the time of diagnosis. Exclusion criteria includes Patients with incomplete medical records. Patients with other significant medical conditions affecting hormonal profiles (e.g., Cushing's syndrome, congenital adrenal hyperplasia).

Data Collection

Demographic Data: Age, ethnicity, and other relevant demographic variables were extracted.

Prescribing Patterns: Details of medications prescribed for PCOS management were recorded, including hormonal contraceptives, insulin sensitizers and anti-androgen medications.

Biochemical Parameters: The following biochemical parameters were collected and analyzed:

Body Mass Index (BMI), Random Blood Glucose levels, Serum levels of Leutinizing Hormone (LH), Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH), Thyroid Profile (TSH, T3, T4), Lipid Profile (Total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, triglycerides).

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 8. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, median, range) were used to summarize continuous variables such as age, BMI, blood glucose levels, hormone levels, and lipid profiles. Categorical variables such as ethnicity and prescribing patterns were summarized using frequencies and percentages.

RESULTS

In this study, a total of 100 female participants aged 15-25 years diagnosed with PCOS were enrolled. Demographic characteristics including age along with BMI distributions and prescribing patterns, are summarized in Table 1. The mean \pm SD age of participants was 28.6 ± 5.2 years. The mean \pm SD was 23.79 ± 4.18 kg/m², Prescribing patterns revealed diverse medication strategies for PCOS management, encompassing hormonal contraceptives, insulin sensitizers, and anti-androgen medications.

Table 1: Demographics, BMI, and Prescribing Patterns

Demographics	
Age (Years) (Mean \pm SD)	28.6 ± 5.2
BMI (kg/m ²) (Mean \pm SD)	23.79 ± 4.18
Prescribing Pattern of Medications	
Total Medications	546
No of Drugs/Prescription (Mean \pm SD)	5.20 ± 0.40
No of Metformin Prescriptions	74
No of anti-androgen prescriptions	52

The Biochemical parameters like serum levels of LH, FSH, Thyroid profile markers, RBS and Lipid Profile parameters are presented in Table 2.

Biochemical Parameter	(Mean ± SD)
Hb (g/dl)	11.08±1.98
LH (mIU/mL)	12.15±5.96
FSH (mIU/mL)	6.31±2.12
RBS (mg/dL)	107±3.14
LDL (mg/dL)	93.98±29.29
VLDL (mg/dL)	29.22±15.91
HDL (mg/dL)	41.48±7.14
TGs (mg/dL)	131.79±69.2
TSH (mg/dL)	2.90±1.75
T3 (ng/dL)	1.25±0.67
T4 (mcg/dL)	8.65±1.67

"Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3 illustrate the correlation between BMI and various biochemical parameters."

Figure 1: BMI and Hb, LH, FSH and RBS

Figure 2: BMI and Lipid Profile

Figure 3: BMI and Thyroid Profile

DISCUSSION

The current study examined the relationship between BMI and several biochemical parameters including lipid profile, thyroid profile, LH, and FSH. Additionally, it analyzed the patterns of medication prescription for managing PCOS. Obesity significantly influences the onset and advancement of PCOS. A considerable number of women with PCOS are obese. Regardless of the extent of obesity, these women often exhibit central (abdominal) fat distribution, linked to

insulin resistance and hyperandrogenism.[11] It is unclear whether lipid metabolism abnormalities are hereditary in families of women with PCOS. However, there is evidence indicating that family members of women with PCOS often exhibit dyslipidemia.[12] It is evident that excessive LH secretion and an elevated LH ratio can disrupt follicle development.[13] The impact of weight loss on LH secretion in women with PCOS is debated. Some studies suggest that weight loss reduces LH secretion [14], while others indicate no significant effect [15, 16]. In lean women with PCOS, increased LH secretion leads to hyperandrogenemia. Conversely, in obese women with PCOS, insulin resistance is considered the primary factor contributing to hyperandrogenism. Thyroid disorders and polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) are prevalent endocrine conditions in the general population. Despite their distinct causes, they share several common characteristics. Primary hypothyroidism, for instance, has been associated with enlarged ovarian volume and cystic changes in the ovaries. Conversely, there is growing recognition that women with PCOS are more prone to thyroid disorders compared to the general population [17-19].

CONCLUSION

Obesity emerges as a significant risk factor in the development and progression of PCOS, characterized by hyperandrogenism and notable alterations in lipid and thyroid profiles. These metabolic changes necessitate the use of multiple drug regimens for effective management of PCOS. Understanding and addressing the interplay between obesity and these biochemical factors is crucial in optimizing therapeutic approaches for individuals with PCOS.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Nil

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